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An Essential Pillar In the U.S: Immigrants

It is ironic that the United States, often described as “a nation of immigrants” and founded on liberty and law, has such a reputation considering its treatment towards immigrants, especially in recent years. Immigration is a complex and controversial issue with both a positive side and a negative side. On one hand they help the country and on the other they bring more problems. The U.S has started to acknowledge these issues but it has also completely ignored the positive impact immigrants have had on the country and is executing all of its plans wrongly. With abuse and unlawful acts, they have mass deported immigrants and closed off borders making it almost impossible for immigrants to come or stay in this country. Now, for the sake of the country, there is no logical benefit or gain from restricting the various aspects of immigration in the U.S. Since the founding of this country immigrants have built this country from the ground up, and they still continue to contribute until today. Immigrants in the U.S have benefited the country more than harming it. While some people still view immigration in the U.S as a safety concern, it is the country's responsibility to support immigrants, as they are the ones who contribute to the economy, morally deserve it, and socially enrich the country.

Historically, most immigration policies have been implemented during times of war to protect the country. Notable examples were the deportations during World War II against the Japanese and during the 2000's when they targeted Muslims after the September 11, 2001 terrorist attack. Now again, to close the borders completely and deport immigrants. Recent issues of immigration in the U.S have popped up a lot in the news due to President Trump's administration's way of enforcing immigration laws and border patrol. It's a hot topic for all and

as a result of his policy's making news more immigration cases have been brought up and the blurry line of how they stand in this country is growing. Cases like Kilmar Abrego Garcia, a Salvadoran man who was wrongfully deported due to error are recurring under this administration. It is an ongoing fight that is, "Chiefly concentrated on the fate of the estimated 11 million unauthorized immigrants in the United States" (Bolter, 1). Hence why immigrants play a major role in the economy.

Immigrants help the economy, they do not just merely live in the U.S, or unbalance the country. They are beneficial to the U.S and their hard work in the economy is shown in studies. A recent study conducted in 2024 analyzed the accounts of immigrants in the labor force, stating that, "Between 2000 and 2022, the foreign born accounted for nearly three-quarters of all growth in the civilian, prime-age (age 25 to 54) labor force" (Gelatt, 1). The immigrant workforce has been a significant part of the labor force in the U.S. economy for a long time. They are the everyday workers and jobs most people do not aim for but are needed in society. Jobs such as construction workers, market workers, and housecleaners are included. As more Americans get older or stray away from these jobs, immigrants are rapidly filling in these positions and if they were not, the economy would collapse. The constant demand and immigrants meeting these demands help sustain the economy as more job opportunities arise and more consumer needs are met. Not only do they work but they also follow the rules of the country. Recent data found that, "Immigrants paid \$382.9 billion in federal taxes and \$196.3 billion in state and local taxes in 2022" (Appleby, 1). From the amount of money immigrants contribute to the country, it is obvious that they have a positive impact. They live in the same country as citizens and in response pay the same taxes for the services this country provides. Immigrants' hard work and taxes are funding school projects, roads, and defense all which are beneficial to the U.S. Yet, the

U.S thinks otherwise and weirdly enough is financially draining our country. One study suggests that maintaining the border costs "Upwards of \$400 billion, but their cost estimate is \$150 billion" (Arrington, 1). From the quote, the cost of securing the borders costs more than letting them open which is absurd considering immigrants' role in the economy. More immigrants mean more money, jobs, and a better economy overall. Eliminating them would be unreasonable because it would limit the country's expansion. It would also be morally wrong for the U.S to do so.

It is morally right for the U.S to foster a safe space for immigrants. Many immigrants from small struggling countries come to succeed and leave their suffering from their country behind. They are refugees seeking opportunities in a new country. For example, Ukrainian immigrants who escaped the war detail in an article that, "The explosions and destruction changed our lives. Outside my window, unarmed civilians and innocent people were killed and shot at" (Khalil, 1). The horrors like the ones described in Ukraine are awful and something anyone would not want to endure. However, the U.S. does not consider this and is doing the exact opposite of what it should be doing as it is abusing and detaining immigrants constantly. Specifically, ICE agents have gotten more aggressive and gained a reputation for it. In Chicago activists said, "Agents threw a canister of a chemical near a school in the city's Logan Square neighborhood" (Tareen, 1). ICE agents are unfair when dealing with immigrants, even going as far as throwing chemical agents which burn the eyes, impact breathing, and in general deteriorate one's health. To go as far as to throw a chemical near a school is so careless and unethical of them. They violate basic human dignity, yet to them these acts of abuse are all in the name of the safety of citizens. In effect, they cause more danger and insecurity in communities. Even when detaining people, they do not listen to them, and reject their legal rights. Their reputation has

made immigrants feel afraid. When picking up their children from school, “The absence of a child—even for a few minutes—can feel like a nightmare come true” (Alveraz, 1). The fear of ICE, being detained, or deported has scared all immigrant families and communities across America. Simple tasks for immigrants such as sending their kids to school cause anxiety because they do not want to be separated from their families. It is a constant wary feeling, especially considering that race plays a central role. Minority groups like Latino, Black, or Brown immigrants are being more targeted for deportation compared to white immigrants due to racism and prejudice. With everything piling up, it is no wonder why even kids are traumatized seeing this occur and why they fear for their lives every day when they shouldn't. The government can not do this to the people and children residing within this nation, it is simply unrighteous.

To continue the list of mistreatments, immigrant minors are being deported, adults are being raided in their work unconstitutionally, and immigrants are being treated badly in prison so they are more willing to leave the U.S. In a specific incident in a Texas immigration detention center, a teen observed, "Adults were forced to compete with children for bottles of clean water when staff left out only a few at a time" (Lauer, 1). The immigrants at the detention center are in poor conditions and could not even receive basic human needs like clean water. The quote also mentions that there are kids at the center, demonstrating the government's no mercy even towards minors. In addition to this, it is very important to mention that the U.S is putting in little to no effort in at least changing their unfair policies or developing a new system. For example, immigrants seeking asylum, people fleeing persecution, find it harder to gain citizenship or a green card even if they have been in the country for decades because of the system. Beyond moral concerns, significant legal violations are occurring today.

It is constitutionally right for the U.S to offer due process as guaranteed by the Fifth

Amendment, yet a recent incident has shown otherwise. In March 2025, the Trump Administration tried to detain Venezuelan nationals who were part of a Venezuelan gang and then as detailed in an article, "The Federal Government started sending scores of Venezuelan...to a foreign prison in El Salvador" (Sotomayor, 1). This situation sparked much controversy because even though they were criminals, this nation's system should not be able to wrongfully send them away without a court case. It is not only unrighteous but it is also against the law. In the end they did end up having hearings due to the violation of the condition but there are still recurring incidents similar to this one. The case proves how the administration is capable of jumping to conclusions and ignoring immigrants knowing that they have no say. Along with these virtuous points for immigration, there is also a social reason for their stay.

The U.S identity and culture are diverse and constantly evolving due to immigration. The U.S is supposed to be an inclusive country for all and it is. It's known as a melting pot of people offering Italian Pizza, German Beer, Chinese restaurants, and more. Although now widely known, American culture is an immigrant culture that has become very widespread. A study conducted revealed that, "In 2015, Chinese restaurants in the U.S. outnumbered all the McDonald's, Burger Kings, and Kentucky Fried Chickens combined.." (Foner, 1). These Chinese restaurants hire Chinese workers, serve Chinese food, and through this spread culinary diversity that current Americans enjoy. They are remaking culture as many know it today. From the food people eat to traditions, clothes, and restaurants, everything has been transformed with the innovations and creativity that immigrants brought with them. They might have also brought more competition but as mentioned in an article, "The presence of immigrants and their offspring has helped "push" American institutions in the direction of increasing openness and meritocracy" (Hirschman, 1). Embracing different cultures and perspectives is not a bad thing. Immigrants

have a positive impact as they encourage American businesses to be more diverse and competitive. Their success has made these businesses want to be more like them, especially considering that immigrants make up most of the U.S population meaning they make up the culture too. When given the chance immigrants are capable of doing what the U.S is meant for, which is creating a socially enriching environment. Nevertheless, disagreements about their presence persists, fueling ongoing debate.

Some may argue that the U.S must control the border for tranquility reasons and to obey the rule of law. In the past years, a lot of criminal immigrants have arrived in this country and have completely bypassed these rules. According to them, "These are predators, abusers, and murderers who should have never been in our country in the first place" (McLaughlin, 1). The administration is securing the stability of the country by getting rid of immigrants, who are unknown people with unknown motives and in this mix are criminals including predators and murderers. Criminal immigrants who are usually illegal, arrive in this country and damage it with violence and terrorism as shown by multiple incidents in the past and present. These people, as stated by the quote should have not been in this country to begin with, and their removal will reduce the worries of the citizens. To add on, the increasing population of immigrants is endangering the country, straining the resources meant for citizens, and some even argue tainting the "American Identity." In a recent 2024 study it was estimated, "That 59 percent of households headed by illegal immigrants use one or more major welfare programs" (Camorata, 2). If the borders continue to be kept open it will encourage more illegal entries and increase the population of immigrants in an already overpopulated country. This means more welfare programs will be used and more money wasted, as shown by the study. Not all of these recent newcomers come for peace and the accumulation of their court cases also makes it unfair for

those who did enter legally or have been in this country for a long time. Despite this, it would also be unfair to cast away the positives of immigration.

The U.S has not done justice to immigrants and their contributions in the economic and social fields as well as their moral case. Although the counterarguments do provide merit, it is crucial to acknowledge that Americans have created many misconceptions about immigration based on fear and stereotypes. Sometimes it just stems from pure racism or jealousy that immigrants have become more successful than the citizens. It is not reasonable to think this way since the U.S has a strict law system that ensures that anyone who disobeys the law gets punished and the U.S is supposed to embrace all. Illegal immigrants should not be treated less than anyone, especially considering many are successful people who create a prosperous society. For example, Albert Einstein, Nikola Tesla, and Elon Musk have all contributed their innovative ideas to the U.S. As stated in a Learn Liberty Article, "From the Ellis Island immigrants who helped build America to the wave of entrepreneurs and skilled workers shaping Silicon Valley" (Coates, 1). Immigrants, like the ones at Silicon Valley, helped provide their input and ideas to the U.S by producing products, filling in jobs, and consuming products. While many immigrants use many welfare programs in the U.S, they also provide the money to support the country and those exact programs. With their constant businesses, taxes, and work, it is clear that immigrants are not the ones who pose a threat. Contrary to popular belief, in Texas, "Undocumented immigrants are arrested at less than half the rate of native-born U.S. citizens for violent and drug crime" (Light, 1). Just because a few immigrants have caused harm doesn't mean all will, as the study indicates. All immigrants face hatred, racism, fear, and the feeling that they do not belong. They know that if they follow the criticism of the opposition, most will face the loss of opportunities and return to troubled countries which is why they are less likely to commit crimes.

It should also be emphasized that there will always be danger in every country, having immigrants in the U.S or not does not affect the crime rates drastically. Since immigrants are helping the economy and benefiting the country in every way they can, it is better to weigh out the pros and the cons for their stay. Even when viewed at a glance it is quite obvious what the answer is.

Although closing the borders is the country's decision, lawmakers should consider the history of the country when making the decision. Many immigrants came for the "American Dream", which is an idea of living to their fullest potential regardless of background and pursuing prosperity in the U.S. An example of this in action is the Californian Gold Rush of 1848 which brought massive amounts of immigrants around the world looking for gold. The idea of prosperity was popular at the country's founding and even received support from the nation itself. Thus, the U.S should stick with its history and continue to pursue its reputation of diversity and welcoming people without discrimination.

It is undeniable to say that in every era, the United States has been shaped by immigrants and their resilience. Therefore, it is only right for the U.S to ensure fair treatment and opportunity for all who seek it. They deserve open borders and the right to stay because they economically benefit it, morality reasons, and have socially helped the country. The conflict of immigrants is what people encourage or not but immigrants throughout the whole entirety of history around the world have only showed dedication to their adopted country. To recognize this legacy is vital for the future of this nation and its citizens. Immigrants are aware of who they are, their actions, and their goals. Why does the U.S have the right to decide their fate when they contribute so much? However, despite bringing success, they have also brought fear into the American world of how they stand, the violence some bring, and their overbearing population.

Immigrants should not be expelled for this, though, their accomplishments outweigh the anxieties and that is what matters the most. It is time for everyone to acknowledge the very starting fabric of the U.S.

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